

Research Article

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Leveraging remittances for financial inclusion and economic development in Zambia: Policy pathways and a conceptual framework

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Abstract: Zambia has seen a surge in remittance inflows of 258% between 2020 and 2024. Despite this increase, the transformative potential for structural economic growth remains limited. This paper develops a conceptual framework that positions remittance as a critical financial intermediation mechanism that is capable of stimulating inclusive growth through productive investment, institutional innovation, and enhanced financial inclusion of citizens. Although remittances have grown rapidly, their impact on the Zambian economy remains largely consumption-oriented, and therefore their impact on economic growth is negligible. There is therefore a need to understand how remittances can transition from household-level support to broader developmental capital that supports national economic transformation. This paper adopts a systematic review of

academic and policy literature and identifies policy incentives, digital infrastructure, and governance quality as mediating variables that determine the developmental impact of remittances. It further draws on various financial theories. The empirical findings are integrated into a multi-level conceptual model, which links macro-economic transformation, micro-economic enhancement, and financial-sector participation and inclusion. The framework provides guidance to policymakers and the financial sector on designing targeted, low-hanging interventions such as digital remittance platforms, remittance-linked financial products, and regulatory reforms. The resulting conceptual model shows how remittances can adapt from consumption-based transfers to productive capital that accelerates national economic growth and financial deepening. The framework offers theoretical and policy foundations for the development of remittance-based development policies and provides a platform for future empirical testing

Keywords – Diaspora engagement, Economic development, Financial inclusion, Remittances, Zambia

1. INTRODUCTION

The emergence of borderless states and the rapid mobility of labour have led to an increase in migrant workers around the world. This migration brings with it a significant increase in remittances of migrant worker remittances. In a number of countries, especially developing countries, migrant remittances now exceed traditional foreign income sources such as overseas direct investments (Ratha et al., 2024). With the increase in remittances, economic-socio-thematic areas such as economic growth, poverty alleviation, and financial sector development are positively

impacted. Remittances sent by migrants are used at a microlevel to cover household expenditure, educational needs, health needs, and the provision of capital for entrepreneurial purposes. The entrepreneurial activities include setting up of small businesses like grocery stores, hair salons, and barber shops, which have the multiplier effect of generating employment opportunities and stimulating local economies. Remittances, therefore, provide a shield against financial shocks and help build micro-economic resilience. At a macro level, there is a significant potential that remittances can form a substantial percentage of a country's Gross Domestic Product (GDP). Remittances consequently result in improved foreign exchange earnings, and this attraction of foreign exchange is an indication of a country's financial stability and economic potential, which is an economic indicator that foreign investors seek prior to investing in a country (Azam et al., 2016).

In Zambia, remittances have increased, especially in the last three decades, and the Zambian diaspora networks have expanded around the world. The Bank of Zambia reports that remittances increased by 258% in five years, from 2, 5 billion Zambian Kwacha in 2020 to 8, 9 billion Zambian Kwacha in 2024 (Table I). Yet, despite this surge, the developmental impact of remittances on the Zambian economy remains negligible or unrecorded.

Table i: Remittance inflows (formal channels only)

Year	Volume of transactions	Value of Transactions (K)
2020	828,108	2,473,386,662.37
2021	1,521,450	4,734,199,544.40
2022	1,602,602	4,117,772,772.80
2023	1,963,698	4,989,016,185.15
2024	2,785,056	8,877,070,721.59

Source: Bank of Zambia website

The paradoxical setting here of high remittance inflows having a low transformational impact raises a few key questions. The first being, what conceptual links explain the transition from household micro-level minor gains to major economic macro-level developmental outcomes? The second question being how these remittances can be leveraged to deepen financial inclusion and financial sector structural transformation? And finally, what institutional, technological, and policy conditions would need to be in place to actualise the potential gains?

The authors (Mulenga, 2013; Chanda, 2015; Bwalya & Phiri, 2015; Kabala, 2023) who have written on the effect of remittances on the Zambian economy and households, provide valuable insights into the poverty-reducing effects of remittances; however, the studies fall short of building an integrated conceptual model linking remittance flows with economic structural change and financial intermediation. The 2019 Zambia Diaspora Policy provides an auspicious framework for engagement but lacks empirical grounding and coherent institutional coordination (Ngáandu & Mumba, 2022; IOM, 2023).

Consequently, this paper seeks to bridge the conceptual and empirical divide by suggesting a new framework that connects the proven micro-economic behaviours of remittance-receiving households with national macro-economic outcomes such as financial deepening, investments, and diversification. The paper argues that the developmental efficacy of remittances would depend mostly on three mediating factors, and these are the public sector and financial sector governance quality and institutional coherence; the policy and regulatory incentives that underline and encourage formalisation of remittance channels, the productive use of the remittances, as well as the digital infrastructure and innovation which enable the efficient use of the remittances.

2. RESEARCH QUESTIONS

How can remittances from Zambians in the diaspora be elevated from current consumption-based household-level transfers to instruments of structural economic transformation and financial inclusion? What policy, institutional, and operational conditions would support this elevation? These questions help in responding to the paradox observed that, despite a significant increase in remittances between 2020 and 2024 (Bank of Zambia, 2025), there appears to be limited evidence of economic-related transformation (Ratha et al., 2024).

3. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A robust theoretical context is essential for the foundation of this study, as it provides the conceptual lenses through which remittances and their developmental potential in Zambia can be systematically stated, given the paradox of increasing remittance inflows with limited transformative impact. The framework provides clarity of the mechanisms through which remittances interact with financial systems, behave as ours, and the wider socio-economic structures. By linking the analysis with established theories, the study explains not only how remittances are used but also why their effects differ in institutional, human development, and financial contexts.

3.1. Financial Intermediary Theory

The Financial Intermediary Theory provides a foundational explanation of how financial institutions transform savings into investments by reallocating resources efficiently across the economy (Levine, 1997). At its centre, the theory posits that financial institutions reduce transactional costs, mitigate information irregularities, and allocate capital efficiently by matching surplus units that are savings with deficit units that are borrowing (Scholtens & Van Wensveen, 2000).

In perspective with the expansion of remittance inflows, financial institutions are placed in a position to act as intermediaries that convert diaspora transfers into deposits, loans, and credit capital. Remittances that enter the financial system through formal financial channels increase deposit bases, thus improving a nation's liquidity and improving financial depth, which are metrics that positively correlate with the growth of gross domestic product (GDP) (IMF, 2025). However, it should be noted that in cases where recipients cash out the remittances immediately, the financial inclusion is nominal and not functional. The distinction between nominal and functional inclusion underscores the need for Zambian financial products linked to remittances. These institutionalised remittance products can include savings accounts, remittance-backed bonds, or diaspora investment funds, to mention a few.

The relevance of this theory to the Zambian remittance landscape becomes apparent when examining the trajectory of remittance flows in the past decade, particularly in the last five years. The financial system can become an important avenue through which remittances can be captured and redirected into economic activity; however, a good number of remittances to Zambia are made through informal remittance channels (IOM, 2023). Empirical studies in sub-Saharan Africa demonstrate that when remittances are made through the formal financial sector, they support financial sector resilience (Aggarwal et al., 2011; Efobi & Asongu, 2016). This also aligns with international studies that illustrate that remittances support the banking system (Barnabé et al., 2021).

3.2. The New Economics of Labour Migration (NELM)

The New Economics of Labour Migration (NELM) framework, developed by Stark & Bloom (1985), views migration not as an individual decision but as a household strategy for risk diversification and income smoothing. The theory posits that households send members abroad to hedge against volatile local financial systems, such as access to capital and credit availability for capital projects, or to improve household consumption. In this regard, remittances are not merely for altruistic reasons, but provide a strategic flow to stabilize household welfare and ensure against local shocks (Taylor, 1999).

NELM also provides a particularly useful framework for understanding the dual role of remittances, both as a

developmental resource and as a coping mechanism. In a country like Zambia, where formal credit markets remain thin and the regulatory and collateral requirements restrict participation of the majority of citizens in the financial sector, especially rural dwellers, remittances provide alternative financial sources for education, micro-enterprises, and asset accumulation. This has been observed in a number of studies across sub-Saharan Africa, where remittances are an informal financial lifeline for households (Lucas & Stark, 1985; Adams & Cuecuecha, 2010).

However, NELM theory not only yields positivity in mitigating vulnerabilities, but it also highlights the importance of institutional and market conditions in shaping developmental outcomes, and where these conditions are weak, so are the developmental outcomes. NELM draws attention to the social and behavioural dimensions of remittances. Research has shown that where institutional support is weak, households are more likely to allocate a greater proportion of their remittances to immediate consumption (Gubert, 2002). This is a dynamic that is observable in Zambia, where remittances are paid on receipt to support short-term needs.

3.3. The Capability Approach

The Capability Approach, as propagated by Sen (1999), gives a human development angle to remittances. It reframes remittances not only as financial monetary flows but also as enablers of personal improvement in areas such as health, financial resilience, education, skills, technology transfer, and entrepreneurship. Through this lens, remittances contribute to expanding the “ability set” of households. However, structural transformation occurs when individual abilities are collated; only then do productive gains occur. These gains can only be achieved if there is systematic coordination between the governance, financial, and policy institutions. When applied to the Zambian context, it shows that remittances have the ability to significantly expand the capability sets of recipient households. Research shows that remittances improve the human capital base of communities (Ajefu & Ogebe, 2021; Hanson & Woodruff, 2003).

Sen (1999), however, reminds us that the relationship between financial resources and improved capabilities is not automatic and is subject to conversion factors. An example is that even if households receive remittances, if there are structural rigidities such as poor healthcare, poor financial infrastructure, and poor educational infrastructure, the capabilities remain stunted. Through this theoretical lens, the study situates remittances as multi-dimensional developmental tools whose impact depends on social, economic, and institutional conversion factors.

4. METHODOLOGY – SYSTEMATIC LITERATURE REVIEW APPROACH

This research adopts a Systematic Literature Review approach due to the limited empirical studies specific to Zambia on remittances. The methodology is designed to evaluate evidence from academic and policy sources between 2000 and 2025, as this provides a longitudinal aspect of the study. The review followed a multi-state process that involved the identification, screening, assessment of eligibility, and final inclusion of relevant studies.

The literature search was conducted on multiple academic and policy-oriented databases to ensure a comprehensive coverage of peer-reviewed journal articles, working papers, and policy reports. The primary databases consulted included Google Scholar, JSTOR, World Bank, and IMF repositories and websites of the African Development Bank, the Southern African Development Community, the International Organisation for Migration, the African Union, and various sites of the Government of Zambia. The searches used Boolean search terms such as remittances, economic growth, financial inclusion, Zambia, Sub-Saharan Africa, policy, governance, and diaspora.

To ensure consistency and relevancy, the inclusion criteria comprised the years of literature articles published between 2000 and 2025, subject to them being credible institutional reports, working papers, and peer-reviewed journal articles. The focus of the review was on developing countries with particular emphasis on sub-Saharan Africa. In addition, the selected articles were required to address the following thematic areas: diaspora remittances relating to structural transformation, digital finance, governance, financial inclusion, economic growth, and household welfare. In contrast, studies were excluded if they were not available in English, lacked empirical or conceptual relevance to remittances, or if they were opinion-based articles with no analytical foundation.

The initial search yielded 120 returns, but after applying inclusion and exclusion criteria, a final set of just under 60 articles formed the basis of the thematic study.

Although the study did not follow the protocol PRISMA (Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews), to ensure methodological robustness, it did adopt the PRISMA principles of transparency, systematic selection, and replicability.

The synthesised review follows a thematic analysis, grouping the evidence under four emergent themes. The themes are as follows.

- Remittances and household welfare;
- Remittances and financial inclusion/ digital transformation;
- Diaspora governance and institutional structures; and
- Economic structural transformation and policy innovation.

4.1. Remittances and Household Welfare

The empirical literature consistently demonstrates the welfare improvements at the household level. The reviewed studies relating to household welfare and poverty reduction all illustrate a positive correlation with remittances. The reviewed studies relating to household welfare and poverty reduction all illustrate a positive correlation with remittances. Zambian author, Mulenga (2013), using the Living Conditions Monitoring Survey (LCMS), found that Zambian households receiving remittances experienced a statistically significant reduction in poverty incidence and severity, especially for external remittances. Another Zambian academic, Mweene (2015), extended this trajectory by illustrating that remittances particularly improved access to healthcare and education, resulting in better welfare at the household level. Another Zambian academic, Mweene (2015), extended this trajectory by illustrating that remittances particularly improved access to healthcare and education, resulting in better welfare at the household level. These findings are consistent with global research that indicates that remittances enhance welfare at the household level and act as a counter-cyclical buffer, assisting smooth household consumption during economic downturns (Abdulai, 2023; Azizi et al., 2024). International evidence further supports the human-enhancing abilities of remittances by funding education, which is a game-changer in poverty alleviation in countries like Zambia (Williams, 2025).

However, these welfare gains remain consumptive, with recipient households using the received funds for immediate needs rather than allocation towards savings or productive investments. This could be the result of either a lack of inclusive financial products targeting remittances and/or limited financial literacy. In some areas, particularly rural areas, remittances also act as a safety net against shocks such as illness, funerals, or natural disasters such as drought or floods (Zingwe et al. 2023). Studies guide that excessive consumption-driven spending may limit capital growth and spur inflation as there are additional funds introduced into the economy, which are not driven by production (Abbas & Islam, 2024).

However, these effects are localised and unstructured. The demand for this “insurance” provides an opportunity for aggregation and reinvestment mechanisms, as the current effects of welfare improvement are unlikely to translate into economic structural development. One gap that exists, however, is the high volume of remittances into Zambia that are made through informal channels and remain unrecorded (Kitimbo, 2021). This presents challenges in assessing the full developmental potential of remittances in Zambia.

4.2. Remittances and financial inclusion/ digital transformation

Digital transformation has emerged as a significant driver of financial inclusion in sub-Saharan Africa. Zambia has made remarkable strides in digital financial inclusion, largely driven by mobile platforms run primarily by Mobile Network Operators (MNO's) such as Zamtel Money, Airtel Money, and MTN Money, and upcoming FinTech's such as Mukuru and Lupiya, to name a few. Authors such as Bwalya and Phiri (2016) discovered that bank accounts or mobile money wallets are more prevalent amongst remittance receiving households, and that illustrated a strong

positive correlation between remittance inflows and financial inclusion. This finding is in line with other African countries that have shown that access to the banking sector and other financial systems has led to improved access to financial products and services, including savings and loan products (Suri & Jack, 2016). On the converse, some writers posit that this sense of financial inclusion is shallow (Kabala, 2023; Mwange & Mwanza, 2023). This is due to the immediate cash-out of remittances once received, precluding the accumulation of savings or their use as access to further credit. Therefore, it is important to establish and develop digital ecosystems that provide interoperable platforms that link banks, FinTechs, and mobile operators as a base for deepening of financial inclusion. Kenya's M-PESA ecosystem is an example of the transformative potential of interoperability (Cracknell, 2023).

The high costs of remittances made through formal channels such as banks remain a prohibitive factor for Zambians in the diaspora. High costs of remittances made through formal channels such as banks remain a prohibitive factor for Zambians in the diaspora. The remittance costs of the sub-Saharan African corridor currently average 8% of sent funds and are amongst the highest in the world (Amponsah et al., 2020; Aurélien et al., 2024). The World Bank (2024) estimates that reducing remittance transaction costs from 8% to 3% in sub-Saharan Africa could release an additional \$5 billion per year into the formal banking sector. Interoperable digital systems reduce remittance costs, and Zambia could benefit significantly from such digitally influenced cost reductions.

4.3. Diaspora Governance and Institutional Structures Policy

The third emerging theme revolves around institutional quality and policy coherence. Institutional frameworks play a decisive role in shaping the developmental impact of remittances. Zambia's 2019 Diaspora Policy articulated a comprehensive framework for diaspora participation, focusing on investment attraction, skills transfer, and remittance use. The slow operationalisation of this progressive document has led to its benefits not being actualized. Studies by Ngáandu and Mumba (2022) and IOM (2023) both highlight the fragmentation and weak inter-institutional coordination by key institutions, as playing a major role in the slow and ineffectual operationalisation of the Diaspora Policy.

The weaknesses are evident in a number of areas. The first being the lack of an integrated remittance database linking the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation, which is the main coordinating institution on diaspora issues, and the Ministry of Finance and National Planning, and the Bank of Zambia, which are the institutions responsible for financial and monetary policy regulation. This absence of an integrated platform undermines evidence-based policymaking. Comparatively, global success stories illustrate the importance of strong governance institutional governance frameworks of governance. Countries with structured and collaborative diaspora engagement have been proven to help accelerate formalising remittances (Orozco & Lopez, 2020). Examples of such countries include India, the Philippines, and even African country Rwanda, to name a few. The minimal participation of the diaspora community in policies regarding diaspora remittances also provides a challenge for remittance beneficiation, which is a symptom of the ineffective roll-out of the Diaspora Policy. Finally, the absence of diaspora-specific financial instruments, such as Bonds or other investment vehicles, is also a noted deficiency in diaspora governance and the potential usefulness of remittances. International studies show that well-designed diaspora bonds strengthen foreign exchange reserves as well as provide finance for capital projects (Plaza & Ratha, 2023).

Studies have shown that fragmented inter-institutional coordination leads to limited developmental outcomes, even in the presence of financial resources (Mtae, 2025). This is the case in the Zambian context of remittances.

4.4. Structural Transformation and Innovation Potential

Taking a macroeconomic perspective, the developmental aspect of remittances depends on the extent to which they are efficiently intermediated into productive sectors. In line with this position, Chanda (2015) found a weak long-term correlation between remittance inflows and GDP growth in Zambia. The primary reasons include low intermediation rates, the absence of remittance-backed investment vehicles, and the proliferation of consumption

expenditures. However, should better institutional quality and policy conditions be in place, remittances can serve as a counter-cyclical stabilisation mechanism, cushioning the national economy during shocks (Nyasulu, 2017; Odhiambo & Musakwa, 2024). There are consistent findings from studies that remittances fail to contribute to structural transformation unless they are channelled through financial systems that encourage savings, investment and credit access.

5. DISCUSSION

The literature review reveals a conceptual paradox: whilst remittances are undeniably enhancing welfare and resilience, their potential for economic transformation is mediated by systemic constraints. At a micro-level, remittances expand household capabilities (Sen, 1999), aiding daily sustenance, education, health, and small-scale businesses, yet in the absence of institutional mechanisms, these gains remain at this entry level, failing to move to the next level of empowerment. At the macro-level, policy and governance gaps inhibit the translation of remittance inflows into economic development. The importance of institutional coherence to channel remittance flows into priority development sectors and to provide incentives that provide for the channelling cannot be overemphasised. At the meso-level, digital inclusion widens access to remittance-based financial services, but fails to transform inclusion into meaningful capital accumulation. This calls for an escalation from access-based inclusion (merely having a financial account that is used mostly for cash-outs) to usage-based inclusion, which leads to saving, investing, and borrowing.

This study singles out three innovative but practical pathways that Zambia can use for economic structural transformation and remittance efficiency. The first being the empowerment of remittance recipients, through financial literacy, to enable them to make productive investment decisions with their received remittances, especially when in excess of current needs. The second is the provision of remittance-backed investment vehicles, such as diaspora bonds, which provide an avenue for both remitters and recipients to invest in. Such vehicles provide an incentive for remittances to be channelled through official channels and not through informal channels (Bandura, Zivanomoyo & Tsurai, 2019), which are popular in sub-Saharan Africa as they are less expensive to use. Remittances have been known to support sectoral diversification by financing microenterprises, agricultural modernization, and SME development, yet in Zambia, the limited availability of structured investment vehicles hinders the expansion of remittance-funded financing. The third practical pathway is the development of digital diaspora investment platforms, which link remitters to verified domestic investment vehicles and enterprises.

This tripartite conceptual model, which posits financial inclusion of both remitter and recipient, is the transmission mechanism through which remittances can drive transformation, but only if moderated by policy incentives, good institutional governance, and digital infrastructure. In Zambia, this trio remains incomplete. Although the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation is the designated lead institution for diaspora coordination, it is under-resourced, as the Diaspora Desk is manned by only one official. Further, despite a robust Diaspora Policy, the policy incentives for diaspora investors are underdeveloped. Although much progress has been made in the financial and digital ecosystems, they are fragmented and expensive. Finally, the weak inter-institutional coordination affects the coherent administration of diaspora remittances. The implication of this is that Zambia's challenge is not in remittance scarcity, but rather inefficiency of remittance, the inability to translate remittance inflows into productive capital.

Figure 1: List of a three-partite conceptual model for Leveraging Remittances for Financial Inclusion and Economic Development in Zambia

The figure above illustrates the transmission mechanism through which remittances influence economic development across micro, meso, and macro levels. The model highlights financial intermediation as the central channel that increases the efficacy of remittances, moderated by digital infrastructure, policy incentives, and governance quality, which jointly determine the developmental impact and efficiency of remittance flows.

6. KEY CONTRIBUTION AND CORE IMPLICATIONS

6.1. Key Contribution

One key reason for this research is that there is a critical gap in academic evidence to explain why remittances received in the country do not correlate with measurable economic benefits arising from the remittances. The contribution of this paper helps close this gap and explain the reasons why the correlation is negligible and therefore advances academic scholarship relating to remittances in Zambia.

To drive macro-economic development, the paper therefore develops an integrated multi-level framework that provides a bridge from earlier studies, which concentrated more on the poverty-reducing effects of foreign remittances from Zambians based in the diaspora (Mulenga, 2013; Mweene, 2015). A key contribution is the introduction of the concept of “remittance efficiency”, which recognises that the remittances received are not channelled into productive avenues and are used predominantly for consumptive purposes. The study, therefore, explores avenues in which remittances can become more efficient and provides an academic record of this. An important contribution is the identification of robust policy incentives, institutional governance quality, formal remittance systems, and digital infrastructure as mediating variables that shift remittances from inefficiency to efficiency (Odhiambo & Musakwa, 2024).

6.2. Core implications

This study strongly illustrates that the challenge is not only in the scarcity of remittances but also the country's inability to convert the surge in remittance inflows into structured productivity gains. Enhancing the remittance ecosystem would have beneficial implications. Ratha et al. (2019) assert that the transformative potential of remittances can only be realised through deliberate institutional coordination and policy frameworks.

6.2.1. Policy implications

Strengthening the developmental role of remittances in Zambia requires a multidimensional approach that will bring together institutional reforms, human capacity development, financial innovation, digital infrastructure, and global and diaspora cooperation. Countries like Nigeria and the Philippines, which have established centralised coordination mechanisms, have illustrated improved policy coherence and enhanced diaspora outcomes such as increased remittances channelled through official channels (Orozco & Lopez, 2020). Whilst the country has a diaspora policy, its implementation is weak; empirical evidence revealed in this study has an impetus to spur both the government and the diasporan community to utilize remittances more efficiently. In Zambia, there is a need to operationalise the existing policy, with the Ministry of Foreign Affairs and International Cooperation taking a lead in ensuring that the policy's objectives are met.

6.2.2. Structural Transformation and Innovation Potential Implications

Effective institutional structures to ensure effective governance of the national remittance system are central to maximising the macro-economic and developmental impact of remittances. The capacitation of the Diaspora Desk and possible upgrading to a Diaspora Unit would ensure all key players work in unison to integrate the Diaspora Policy and diaspora strategies, thereby reducing institutional fragmentation, as well as streamlining regulatory oversight. This would also improve diaspora engagements. Furthermore, the strengthening of the centralised unit would provide a repository for capturing both informal and formal remittances, improving macro-economic forecasting, and thereby providing evidence-based policy making. Studies have shown that countries with robust data systems are better able to leverage them for enhanced management of external sector opportunities and vulnerabilities (Akanle et al., 2022).

6.2.3. Human Capacity development and Financial Literacy development

Human capital development is a thread that runs through any developmental agenda and remains indispensable to optimise the long-term benefits of remittances. Financial literacy programmes are the cornerstone for remittance recipients, especially those who use remittances only to cash out. These programmes can shift financial behavior from consumption-based to savings/investment-based. Empirical studies have shown that financial literacy interventions increase the propensity to save or invest (Xu & Zia, 2012; Dermirguc-Kunt et al, 2022). Another human

capacity aspect is the engagement of diaspora organisations to build mentoring and skills transfer networks, including helping the Zambian government with lessons learnt from their host nations (Mueller, 2022).

6.2.4. Financial Innovation

Financial deepening is essential in transforming remittances from consumption-based to productive purposes. Setting up remittance-to-investment platforms provides a ready mechanism that gives the diaspora community a one-point avenue that facilitates diaspora participation. Such platforms may provide a gateway to various ventures such as investment in real estate, agribusiness, manufacturing, and energy, to name a few. Evidence from Kenya and Rwanda shows that digital investment platforms can increase diaspora participation in national economic development initiatives (Munyegera & Matsumoto, 2018). Two successful financial innovations that can be accessed through a digital investment platform are Remittance-linked savings accounts and Diaspora Bonds, which would have preferential foreign-exchange and interest rates. Diaspora bonds have been effectively leveraged in countries like Nigeria and Ethiopia, as Capital-to-Finance specific projects and build foreign exchange reserves (Ketkar & Ratha, 2010; Plaza & Ratha, 2023).

6.2.5. Digital infrastructure

The expansion of the digital infrastructure is a critical enabler of efficient and affordable remittance transfers. For a country like Zambia, which has an active mobile money environment, interoperability between mobile money service providers and the formal banking system can significantly increase remittance volumes as well as reduce transaction costs. Studies in East Africa illustrate that interoperability between mobile money providers and commercial banks reduces transaction fees by up to 30% (GSMA, 2022). One of the risks that comes with the use of mobile money wallets is the weak Know-Your-Customer (KYC) frameworks, which makes commercial banks hesitant in supporting the interoperability of the two systems; however, this provides an opportunity for digital KYC innovations (Arner et al., 2020).

6.2.6. Behavioural Shifts

In addition, behavioural patterns in both senders and recipients of remittances are likely to shift with the realisation of missed opportunities for productive economic gain. The continued reliance on informal transfer channels, often preferred due to their speed, accessibility, lower cost, and minimal documentation requirements, is an area which requires a major shift in behaviour. It should be noted that achieving this requires not only regulatory enforcement but also an alignment of incentives that can appeal to both senders and recipients. It is worth noting that there is also a trust deficit, which tends to underpin the persistent use of informal channels; however, with improved governance, transparency, and service reliability, the shift to using formal transmission channels is bound to rise. The aggregation of both hard and behavioural measures should not only achieve mindset change, but also enhance the traceability, efficiency, and developmental utilisation of remittances.

7. LIMITATIONS AND SUGGESTIONS FOR FUTURE STUDIES

As the existing body of literature on Zambian remittances relies heavily on formal data sources such as LCMS, valuable information, such as substantial remittance inflows made through informal transmission channels is excluded. This omission produces underestimated remittance magnitudes, thus narrowing both policy relevance and empirical insight. Secondly, the predominance of urban-based studies obscures rural experiences and temporal dynamics, thereby not providing a full impact in all geographical areas. Furthermore, the current literature has yet to fully unravel consumption uses from investment effects, a difference that is core to evaluating the long-term effects of remittances.

Future research should therefore pursue actionable recommendations on how to accelerate the implementation

of the objectives of the policy. Other actions should include the quantification of the large number of remittance inflows that occur outside formal systems, and how these can be brought into formal inflow systems for the use of macro-development. Most of the current studies are based on datasets that are static; therefore, future research should be longitudinal and tracked over a period of time. Further research could be able to offer a more nuanced understanding of Zambia's remittances, and therefore the field remains open for deeper interdisciplinary and policy-oriented inquiry research. These studies would not only provide pathways to transform Zambia's remittance boom into a structural development engine but also refine the empirical contribution to remittance studies.

8. CONCLUSION

This study proposes a conceptual framework indicating how remittances can be leveraged for economic structural transformation and financial inclusion in Zambia. Drawing from NELM, Capability Approach, and Financial Intermediation Theory, the framework conceptualises remittances as a way above household transfers, but as developmental flows that can be used to develop the country's economic growth agenda.

The evidence shows that despite the fact that Zambia's remittance flows are increasing significantly, their transformative impact is limited by governance fragmentation, inadequate policy incentives, low levels of financial literacy, and limited digital integration. The proposed model and framework provide both a policy blueprint for action and an analytical foundation for future empirical research. The key action takeaways that would transform remittances into engines of growth are the following:

- Formalising flows through formal and accessible digital systems;
- Aggregating transfers through formal platforms into an investment pool; and
- Institutionalising the engagement of the diaspora through cohesive governance structures.

These practical but impactful measures can position remittances as strategic instruments for the achievement of inclusive and sustainable economic growth.

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